

Mixing Livestock in a Forest: Silvopastoralism

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Cows and goats in mixed grazing in Evrytania- Greece (photo G. Bakogiorgos)

Mixed grazing is defined as the grazing of two or more livestock species (e.g. cows, goats and sheep) at the same time. This mixed grazing offers multiple benefits, such as full utilisation of pasture (different animal species use different plants or different parts of the same plants), successful weed control and biomass reduction, improved soil fertility and health, increased biodiversity and increased profit for the farmer. Improving the level of protection against large predators is also important. In addition, the establishment of mixed herds reduces the business risk of a livestock farm, since the outbreak of a fatal disease for one species will not result in the total destruction of the livestock farm.

The formation of mixed flocks of sheep and goats is a common practice in Greece since ancient times. However, the establishment of mixed herds of cattle with small ruminants is not an easy task since small ruminants show a general aversion to the presence of cattle especially near water supply points. This difficulty can be overcome either by compulsory co-existence due to space constraints (as is the case in the village of Stenoma in Evritania) or by special techniques to create a 'bond' between sheep or goats and cattle. Indeed, the development of a 'bond' is such that a flock of sheep can follow any herd of cattle and not specific animals.

The optimum use of available pasture can be achieved by adding individuals of a second species to a pasture. Thus, according to the literature, a herd of 200-300 sheep can be added to a pasture where a herd of 200 cattle is grazing without affecting the productivity of the cattle and at the same time improving the economic result of the farm.

In general, mixed grazing of cattle with small ruminants is a very good technique to overcome problems of space constraints, especially in mountainous areas where conflicts and competition for land between farmers prevail.

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